

**Geocoding Child Sexual Abuse: An Explorative Analysis on Journey to Crime and to
Victimization from French Police Data**

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Introduction

Sexual abuse against children has been studied from many perspectives and in various disciplines. Decades of research established a common ground of knowledge about the heterogenous nature of child sexual offending, the variety of offenders characteristics and the necessity to separate these types of sexual crimes from others (Chopin, 2017; Chopin & Beauregard, in press; Ciavaldini, 1999; Gravier, Mezzo, Abbiati, Spagnoli, & Waeny, 2010; Kaufman and colleagues, 1998; Rebocho & Gonçalves, 2012; Smallbone & Wortley, 2001). Still, more research is needed and, among the many aspects to investigate further, one potential focus is the distance traveled by offenders and victims to crime places.

Environmental Criminology as Theoretical Framework

Already in the 1920s, the Chicago School advocated the link between movement, human behavior and crime. Burgess (1925) evoked movement from one social location to another as carrier of a possible/probable cultural decadence, weakened social control and then criminal behavior. For the first time in the history of criminology, researchers came across the idea of mobility triangle conceived as the geometric visualization of a single crime with three apexes: the place of crime (1), the victim (2) and the offender's residence (3). In 1971, Amir adopted the geometric construction of mobility triangle to study rape characteristics in Philadelphia. Since the '70s, that branch of discipline -which falls under the name of environmental criminology- strengthened its theoretical and empirical contribution on the influence of geography on crime and on crime decision-making.

The paradigm behind environmental criminology is based on rationality of human decisions which assumes that people minimize efforts and maximize benefits (Cornish & Clarke, 1986; Felson & Clarke, 1998). In this sense, offenders and victims have routine activities (i.e. going to work, going home, going to restaurants) and, when a crime occurs, this

is the result of a convergent setting where offender and victim are on the same place at the same time without any capable guardian (i.e., police officer or house alarms) (Cohen & Felson, 1979, (Brantingham & Brantingham, 1993). Rationality in offenders' decision-making should be intended as bounded by their personal experiences, self-control and daily activities. Thus, it explains why some offenders commit a crime under certain circumstances while others not (Clarke & Cornish, 2000).

Environmental Criminology and Sexual Assault

This theoretical framework has been applied several times in the field of child abuse (see Beauregard, Leclerc, & Lussier, 2012; Leclerc, Chiu, & Cale, 2016; Leclerc & Felson, 2016; Leclerc, Smallbone, & Wortley, 2014, 2015; Leclerc, Wortley, & Smallbone, 2011; Wortley & Smallbone, 2006, 2010). In this framework, the geometry of crime provides more information on “modus operandi”, which has been defined as “the actions taken by an offender to perpetrate the offense successfully” (Douglas, Burgess, Burgess, & Ressler, 2006, p. 353). Nowadays, geographic information systems have facilitated a more detailed analysis on crime. Several studies have investigated the spatial behavior of offenders and victims of violent crimes and property crimes (e.g., Block & Bernasco, 2009; Block, Galary, & Brice, 2007; Brown, 1982; Groff & McEwen, 2005; LeBeau, 1987a). Even for adult sexual abuse, research suggests the relevance of spatial behaviours and their correlation to factors characterizing offenders, victims and crimes (see Beauregard, Proulx, & Rossmo, 2005). The manuscript reviews the state of the art regarding the spatial patterns of sexual delinquency, and the “modus operandi” (i.e., crime characteristics) of sexual abuse with a focus on child sexual abuse. Based on the literature review, this study analyzes the individual characteristics (i.e., sociodemographic, lifestyle and routine activities characteristics) and “modus operandi” factors (i.e., crime characteristics, scenes of crime parameters, offenders and victims relationship) influencing the spatial behavior in a large dataset of child sexual abuse.

Spatial Behavior and Sex Assaults

Journey to Crime

The spatial behavior of sexual offenders has been studied by criminologists for many years (for a review see Beauregard and colleagues, 2005). Generally, findings indicate that sexual offenders do not travel far to assault their victims. In other words, when potential victims live far from offenders, they are less likely to be assaulted. This phenomenon is known as the distance decay pattern and has been observed in several studies (Alston, 1994; Andresen, Frank, & Felson, 2014; Block and colleagues, 2007; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; Davies & Dale, 1995; LeBeau, 1987a, 1987b, 1987c, 1992). The exception to the distance decay pattern is called the buffer zone (Brantingham & Brantingham, 2008). This is the area around the offender's residence and is where he perceives committing a crime to be too risky due to the possibility of being recognized. For sexual crimes, results on the existence of buffer zones are mixed (e.g., Canter & Gregory, 2008; Davies & Dale, 1995). Few studies have investigated the spatial behavior of sexual assault victims (also known as the journey to victimization). For example, in the study of Chopin and Caneppele (2018) a majority of adult victims are assaulted near their residences and more than 50% within a distance of 0.75 km from their living spaces (victim's residence).

Mobility Crime Triangle Analysis

Groff and McEwen (2007) used the geometric construct of mobility crime triangle to connect the place of crime to an offender's residence and a victim's residence. Other studies have done the same for sexual crimes but none of them have looked at sexual abuse against children (Amir, 1971; Andresen, Felson, & Frank, 2012; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018). Amir (1971) showed that, in the majority of extrafamilial sexual crimes, offenders and victims are living in the same area. Andresen and colleagues (2012) indicated that mobility triangle

patterns change when co-offending or multiple victims are involved. For extrafamilial sexual crimes, Chopin and Caneppele (2018) have confirmed the relevance of the mobility crime triangle. In their study (N=1,447), 11.82% of offenders and victims lived in the same neighborhood, 33.10% of offenders moved out of neighborhood (400 m) to commit an assault, and 9.54% of victims moved farther than 400 m before being assaulted. In most cases (42.78%), the distance among the three apexes (place of crime, offender and victim residence) was more than 400 m.

Specific Case of Child Abuse

Studies on the spatial patterns of child sex abuse are rare. To the best of our knowledge, only one publication provides information concerning the distance between an offender's residence and the place of crime. Proulx and Ouimet (1995) observed the spatial behavior of nine pedophiles. In three cases, the offenders and victims were strangers, whereas in the other cases, the victims knew their offenders at the time of the offense. Their findings showed that in cases where the offenders and victims were strangers, the offenders traveled farther (1 to 40 km) than in other cases (0 to 1 km).

Links Between Individual Factors and Modus Operandi of Child Abuse

As pointed out by Beauregard and colleagues (2005), the relationship between the distance traveled and the modus operandi is a central question. Likewise, it is relevant to investigate the link connecting people's spatial behavior and individual factors. Some studies on adult victims showed stronger correlations between spatial behavior and modus operandi (i.e., crime characteristics) compared to individual characteristics (Beauregard and colleagues, 2005; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; LeBeau, 1987a). In the field of child abuse, researchers have mostly investigated the link between the victim's characteristics, the offender's characteristics, and the modus operandi (Kaufman and colleagues, 1998; Leclerc, Proulx, & Beauregard, 2009).

Victims Characteristics

Concerning the victims, Smallbone and Wortley (2000) showed that the majority of children were approached by their abusers at a friend's home (36.5%), while in their own neighborhoods (17%), during babysitting (17%), or through organized activities (18.9%). Exploring the routine activities of young victims at the time of the assault, Leclerc and Felson (2016) demonstrated that the majority of victims were engaged in conventional indoor activities (e.g., playing, watching TV, or staying with a babysitter) while the minority were involved in conventional outdoor activities (e.g., playing games outside, swimming, or going to the park). The cases in which victims were engaged in marginal activities and/or in forbidden activities were anecdotal (Leclerc & Felson, 2016).

Offenders Characteristics

By analyzing the offender's characteristics, Kaufman and colleagues (1998) found more violent behaviors and more sophisticated strategies among young offenders. Leclerc, Carpentier, and Proulx (2006) also found that adolescent abusers are more likely to use manipulative strategies. When victims are children, the presence of sexual deviance among offenders is most relevant (Chopin, 2017; Gravier and colleagues, 2010; Leclerc, Proulx, & Beaugard, 2009). Leclerc and colleagues (2006) showed that sexual offenders with deviant fantasies are more likely to adopt sophisticated modus operandi strategies. Kaufman and colleagues (1998) found that extrafamilial child sex abusers often consume alcohol and drugs with victims in order to get their cooperation.

Modus Operandi and Crime Characteristics

The modus operandi and crime characteristics of child abuse suggest that, for most cases, offenders and victims are acquaintances at the time of the offense (Gravier and colleagues, 2010; Proulx & Ouimet, 1995; Smallbone & Wortley, 2000). However, other studies found an equitable distribution between stranger and non-stranger offenders (Chopin,

2017; Elliott, Browne, & Kilcoyne, 1995). The relationship between offenders and victims influences both the environment and the modus operandi through which sexual assaults occur (Leclerc and colleagues, 2016). In many cases, offenders are focused on the necessity of obtaining a child's confidence (Leclerc, Proulx, Lussier, & Allaire, 2009). In a study concerning the predatory behavior of child abusers, Rebocho and Gonçalves (2012) distinguished three types of approaches suggested by Beauregard, Rebocho, and Rossmo (2010). Their results indicated that most child molesters are manipulative offenders (86.6%) who premeditate their crimes and select known victims in close spatial proximity (Rebocho & Gonçalves, 2012).

Studies concerning the nature of the abuse are not convergent. In some of them (Elliott and colleagues, 1995; Leclerc, Proulx, Lussier, and colleagues, 2009), the sexual offenses committed are mostly acts of sexual penetration. In other research (Chopin, 2017; Gravier and colleagues, 2010; Kahn & Chambers, 1991; Leclerc and colleagues, 2014) findings indicated that cases involving sexual penetration were fewer. These differences could be due to the specificity of data used (Leclerc and colleagues, 2016) and thus, the various types of offenders and the contexts of crime. Following an environmental criminology perspective, criminologists have also studied the location where child sexual abuses have occurred. Smallbone and Wortley (2000) found that 45.8% of extrafamilial child sexual abuse were committed at the offender's residence, 25.4% during a car ride, and 23.7% in an isolated place. Lang and Frenzel (1988) found that extrafamilial sexual assaults occurred more often in the offender's house (54%), in the victim's house (44%), or in a vehicle (14%). These results have been corroborated by other studies where the offender's residence was the most common place of aggression (Chopin, 2017; Leclerc, Wortley, & Smallbone, 2010). Generally, extrafamilial child abuse occurs during an offender's routine activities. The relationship between the offender and the victim determines the place of crime (Leclerc and colleagues, 2016).

Aims of Study

The goal of this study is twofold: Identify spatial patterns of child abuse and compare them with adult patterns. Specifically, this research investigates the association of different victim, crime and offender characteristics with pre-defined spatial mobility patterns by combining spatial information (i.e., offense, victim, and offender addresses) with individual (i.e., sociodemographic and lifestyle) and modus operandi characteristics (i.e., crime parameters). The study aims to:

- Investigate the distribution of the distances between offender's residences, the victim's residences, and the places of crime. In particular, this analysis will explore whether the distribution of distances follows a decay pattern as is commonly observed in studies on sexual abuse of adults (Alston, 1994; Andresen, Frank, & Felson, 2014; Block and colleagues, 2007; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; Davies & Dale, 1995; LeBeau, 1987a, 1987b, 1987c, 1992);
- Investigate whether geometry of crime is a promising approach for research on child abuse. In particular, this analysis will discuss whether the crime mobility triangle is a useful construct, as is observed in studies on sexual abuse of adults (Amir, 1971; Andresen, Felson, & Frank, 2012; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018);
- Investigate the role modus operandi on mobility patterns in extrafamilial child sexual abuse. In particular, this analysis will discuss whether modus operandi affects mobility patterns better than sociodemographic and lifestyle characteristics of offenders and victims, as is observed in studies on sexual abuse of adults (Beauregard and colleagues, 2005; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; LeBeau, 1987a).

Methods

Sample

The study considered 612 solved cases of sexual abuse against children committed in an extrafamilial context between 1979 and 2013 in France. The sample comes from a national police database which integrates information files collected throughout the investigation by multiple actors (police detective, coroner, psychologist, etc.). In order to avoid missing data, information is aggregated and compiled in the database by crime analysts that are experts in sexual assault. Overall, the study considered 97.60% of all cases in the database (N=627) and it includes those cases which fulfill four requirements: a) offender's residence, victim's residence and place of crime are identifiable (in 2.40% of cases one of the three addresses were missing); b) for each sexual abuse, there is only one offender and one victim to avoid the bias of multiple offenders/victims described by Andresen and colleagues (2012); c) the offender is not a serial child abuser and d) the child has been victim of child abuse only once in life. Of course, we cannot exclude that some offenders or some victims in the sample are known to police for one case whereas they are implied in one or more unreported or unsolved cases of child abuse.

In this research, a child victim is aged under 15 years old at the time of the offense. This is consistent with the French criminal code, since in France the age of 15 years old corresponds to sexual majority.

Operationalization of Geographical Data

In order to calculate the straight-line distances, also named Euclidean distances, between the three apexes (place of crime, offender and victim residence), we computed the XY (longitude and latitude) coordinates based on addresses that were automatically geocoded. In a second time, by linking these three apexes, mobility triangles were generated. This enabled the identification of the mobility triangle patterns described in literature (Chopin & Caneppele,

2018; Groff & McEwen, 2007) in which they are subdivided into two typologies: the geometric patterns of crime and the geographic patterns of crime.

The geometric patterns of crime can be split into three categories: dots, lines, and triangles. Dots represent cases where offenses occur at the same address (not necessarily the same apartment) where both the offender and victim are living at the time of the offense. With line patterns, two out of the three locations for the crime are the same. Finally, triangle patterns involve cases where the three places implicated in the crime are different.

The geographic patterns of crime give a more complete overview of criminal mobility through five patterns. The first one (the neighborhood pattern) occurs when none of the addresses are farther than 400 m from each other. In the second group of patterns, only one address is farther than 400 m away. This may be the case for the offender's residence (offender mobility), victim's residence (victim mobility), or place of aggression (offense mobility). In the last geographic pattern (the total mobility pattern), all the addresses are farther than 400 m from each other.

The 400 m standard distance is based on its common use in the transit system to identify areas accessible on foot (Aultman-Hall, Roorda, & Baetz, 1997; Boehmer, Hoehner, Wyrwich, Ramirez, & Brownson, 2006; El-Geneidy, Grimsrud, Wasfi, Tétreault, & Surprenant-Legault, 2014; Pikora and colleagues, 2006; Sampson, 1986; Simon, Kwan, Angelescu, Shih, & Fielding, 2008). This distance has also been used by criminologists for American and European studies (Amir, 1971; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; Groff & McEwen, 2007).

Variables

Dependent and independent variables are based on the literature presented in the first part of this study. The two mobility patterns of crime typologies constitute the dependent variables; the first one concerns the above-mentioned geometric patterns of crime divided into three modalities (dot, line, and triangle) while the second dependent variable is based on the

geographic typology of crime with five modalities (neighborhood mobility, offender mobility, victim mobility, offense mobility, and total mobility). Each modality is a dichotomous dependent variable (coded in 0-1).

In this research 39 independent variables are tested and can be classified in two groups; the first group of 23 variables concerns the personal and social characteristics of the victims and offenders (individual characteristics) and the second group include 16 variables describing the modus operandi and crime characteristics. All these variables are dichotomous (0-1) except for one variable relating to the age of offenders at the time of the offense.

To describe the victims characteristics, 13 variables are considered. The first concerns the sex of victims: Victim is a female. The age variable has been divided according to the different stages of childhood: 0 to 2 years old (early childhood), 3 to 9 years old (childhood), 10 to 12 years old (pre-adolescence), and 13 to 14 years old (adolescence). We broke down the age in four classes on the assumption that mobility patterns vary during the developmental steps. To build the childhood category we decided to follow partially the methodology used by Finkelhor, Turner, Ormrod, and Hamby (2009). In their study, they considered that victims under the age of 9 years old have similar routine activities (Finkelhor and colleagues, 2009). Nevertheless, we decided to create a specific category for child younger than three years old.

The following variables are relating to the routine activities of victims when they were assaulted: domestic activities (e.g., watching TV), sleeping, school activities, babysitting, playing, traveling to or from somewhere (i.e., this variable describes cases where victims move from one place to another independently of the travelled distance that could be very short), sports or recreational activities and visiting friends and relatives.

To describe offenders, 10 variables are considered and only one (age) is continuous. All other variables are dichotomous (0-1). The variables used to characterize the offenders are: Offender is a male, age, offender is single, offender lives with nobody. Variables relating to

the offenders' lifestyle are: offender consumes alcohol, offender consumes drugs, offender like to socialize/party (i.e., offender participates in social events where other people are present), offender is a loner (i.e., offender avoid social contact), offender is frequently engaged in criminal activities (i.e., offender has previous convictions), evidence of paraphilic behavior (offender have been detected to have paraphilia and/or sexual deviances).

To describe modus operandi and crime characteristics, 16 dichotomous (0-1) variables have been analyzed; victim and offender are strangers, victim and offender are acquaintances, offender used con approach (e.g., befriended the victim, posed as an authority figure, offered assistance, etc.), surprise approach (e.g., lay in wait inside a building, grabbed the victim, etc.), blitz approach (e.g., offender grabbed and immediately choked the victim, offender immediately overpowered the victim, offender immediately hit the victim, offender immediately stabbed or shot the victim, etc.). Other variables are related to the place of crime parameters: residence (e.g., victim's residence, offender's residence, single-family dwelling, multi-family dwelling, third party residence), offender workplace, transportation related location (e.g., offender's motor vehicle, taxi, school bus, city bus, subway), entertainment location (e.g., bar, nightclub, circus, carnival, bowling), public building (e.g., school, library, hospital, public washroom), outside or inside place, offender is familiar with the place of crime. Variables concerning the type of sexual aggression are: sexual penetration (i.e., vaginal and anal penetration with a penis or a foreign object), sexual touching, fondling (i.e., fellatio, cunnilingus, masturbation). The last variable, describes the presence of weapons during the crime (this variable is considered even if the weapon has not been used).

Analytical Strategies

Through a descriptive analysis, we observed the distribution of the three distances (offender living place-place of crime, victim living place-place of crime, and offender living place-victim living place) in increments of 10 km. Subsequently, we detailed the distance

distributions within increments of 250 m. in the first 5 km. Then, we created the geometric and geographic patterns of crime by combining the three distances in all cases.

Secondly, we proceeded in bivariate and multivariate analyses. Chi-square, including Cramer's V/Phi coefficients (i.e., for dichotomous variables) and Kruskal-Wallis test (i.e., for continuous variable) have been considered to identify differences in the distribution of the proportion of each independent variable in relation to the geometric patterns of crime. When the cell count cell count was insufficient to justify chi-square tests, the Fisher's exact significance was used. Based on the differences found at the bivariate level, multivariate analyses were computed with binomial logistic regressions. We compared each type of dependent variable related to the geographic patterns of crime. In order to increase the quality of the final model, regressions were configured using the stepwise method. Despite the fact that we have more than two categories in the dependent variable, five binomial logistic regressions, instead of multinomial logistic regression were applied. The goal of this analysis is to compare, at a multivariate level, each category of the triangle mobility typology with the remainder of cases. In one category, the sample size is too limited to provide empirical validity with multinomial regression (i.e., offense mobility consists of only 11 cases). Being based on a theoretical classification, it is not possible to reclassify data and in this perspective, each modality of the dependent variable was tested as a reference category in comparison to the other cases. The model includes only the independent variables that presented significant differences at the bivariate level. All these analyses have been performed on the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS V24.0). Ethical approval was obtained to conduct this research.

Results

Journeys to Crime and Victimization

Table 1 shows, by increments of 10 km, how far offender and victim have traveled from their residence to the place of crime. Generally, the distances traveled are less than 10 km. This is true both for offenders (72.88%) and victims (88.24%). Unsurprisingly, most of offenders and victims lives closer than 10 km (78.76%).

[PLEASE INSERT TABLE 1 HERE]

Figure 1 provides an overview on journey to crime and victimization within a distance of 5 km (for details see Appendix 1). It emerges that, most of child sexual abuses are committed close to where offender and victim live, while they are more rarely moving away from their home (distance decay pattern). For example, most of the victims (58.17%) were assaulted at a distance of less than 0.5 km from their residences and most of the offenders were living less than 2.5 km from the places of crime (50.65%). 52.29% of victims and offenders were living at a distance of less than 1 km apart.

[PLEASE INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE]

Crime Mobility Triangles

Geometrically, crime mobility triangles result from connecting three apexes (place of crime with offender's and with victim's residence). In our sample of extrafamilial child sexual abuses, crime is committed mostly either where the offender lives or where the victim lives (line patterns: 43.30%). While for 38.73% of cases sexual abuse happens in a different location from where offender and victim's residence (triangle pattern), in a minority of cases (17.97%) the abuse takes place in the same location (apartment or building) where both offender and victim established their residence (dot pattern). Geographically, crime mobility triangles help to detect inside/outside neighborhood displacements. In our sample, 27.29% of child sexual abuses have been committed inside the same neighborhood where offender and victim live

(neighborhood mobility pattern). In other cases: a) offender moves to the victim's neighborhood to commit the crime (offender mobility pattern, 27.78%); b) crime happens in a third neighborhood, and offender and victim live in other different neighborhoods (total mobility pattern, 25.98%); c) victim moves to the offender's neighborhood where s/he is abused (victim mobility pattern, 17.16%), or d) crime happens in a third neighborhood, if both offender and victim live in the same neighborhood (offense mobility patterns 1.80%).

[PLEASE INSERT TABLE 2 HERE]

Individual Factors, Crime Parameters and Mobility

Table 3 presents bivariate findings concerning individual characteristics (offenders and victims). Victims aged between 3 y/o and 9 y/o are more often assaulted at home or at the offender's residence (dot and line patterns). Pre-teen victims (10 y/o to 12 y/o) and teen victims are more often assaulted in another place than their residence or than the offender's residence (triangle pattern). Their routine activities affect the geometric pattern of crime. However, while sexual abuse occurs more often when victims are walking or practicing sports/recreational activities (triangle pattern); assaults occur more often in the context of domestic activities, when victims are sleeping, being babysat, playing with friends, or visiting friends (dot or line patterns).

Offender characteristics are less closely linked with mobility than those of their victims. Offenders who are living alone and/or who have active social lives are a little more likely to assault in a line pattern. Offenders with paraphilic deviances assault their victims more often in a dot or line pattern than in a triangle one.

[PLEASE INSERT TABLE 3 HERE]

Table 4 describes analysis of the modus operandi and crime characteristics show differences about the relationship between offenders and victims at the time of the offense. Stranger relationships occur mostly in triangle patterns whereas acquaintance relationships are

mostly present in dot and line patterns. The con approach is more often used in a dot or line mobility pattern than in a triangle one, while coercive approaches are more often used in triangle mobility patterns. Regarding the places of crime, assaults occurring in a dot or line pattern happen more often in residence (i.e. of the offender, the victim, or a third party). In triangle patterns, sexual abuse occurs more often in the offender's workplace, in transportation-related locations, in entertainment locations, in public places, or outdoor. Generally, offenders are more familiar with the place of crime in a dot or line mobility pattern. Concerning the type of acts committed, results show that the performance of sexual acts is more complete in dot mobility patterns. Moreover, the study shows that offenders are more often carrying a weapon in a triangle pattern.

[PLEASE INSERT TABLE 4 HERE]

Table 5 presents the findings of a multivariate analysis for geographic patterns of crime.

In Model 1, the reference category is the neighborhood mobility pattern (27.29% of cases). According to Nagelkerke R^2 , this model explains 37.3% of the variance. Findings indicate that neighborhood mobility pattern is more likely to happen when victims are aged between 3 and 9 years old ($\beta = 1.14, p < .001$). Victims are more at risk of being assaulted when they are traveling in their own neighborhoods ($\beta = 0.93, p < .01$). Offenders are more likely to have paraphilic disorders ($\beta = 0.39, p < .05$), and they are more often known to their victims at the time of the offense ($\beta = 1.71, p < .001$). In addition, offenders are more often familiar with the scene of crime ($\beta = 1.61, p < .05$), and sexual touching is the most common act of assault ($\beta = 0.68, p < .05$). On the contrary, in neighborhood mobility patterns, offenders have often less active social lives ($\beta = -1.51, p < .01$), and they less frequently live alone ($\beta = -0.63, p < .05$) and bring a weapon less frequently ($\beta = -2.59, p < .001$). They assault victims less often in their workplaces ($\beta = -1.69, p < .01$) or in transportation-related locations ($\beta = -1.53, p < .001$).

In Model 2, the reference category is the offender mobility pattern (27.78% of cases). According to Nagelkerke R^2 , this model explains 22% of the variance. In this mobility scheme, crimes are more likely to occur when victims are aged between 3 and 9 years old ($\beta = 0.73$, $p < .05$) or 10 and 12 years old ($\beta = 0.76$, $p < .05$) and when they are engaged in domestic activities ($\beta = 0.72$, $p < .001$). In this pattern, assaults occur most often in residences (the victim's residence; $\beta = 1.30$, $p < .001$) or in transportation-related locations ($\beta = 1.11$, $p < .01$).

In Model 3, the reference category is the offender mobility pattern (17.16% of cases). According to the Nagelkerke R^2 , this model explains 21% of the variance. Crimes are more likely to occur when victims are being babysat ($\beta = 0.71$, $p < .05$) or visiting friends ($\beta = 0.96$, $p < .001$). They occur less frequently when victims are aged between 3 and 9 years old ($\beta = -0.71$, $p < .01$) and when they are engaged in domestic activities ($\beta = 1.09$, $p < .05$) or are traveling ($\beta = -1.02$, $p < .01$). In this pattern, offenders are more likely to know their victims ($\beta = 0.73$, $p < .05$).

In Model 4, the reference category is the offense mobility pattern (1.80% of cases). Despite the fact that the Nagelkerke R^2 suggests that this model explains 41% of the variance, it should be interpreted with caution because it is a rare event (only 11 cases) (for details on methodological implications of rare events see King & Zeng, 2001; Peduzzi, Concato, Kemper, Holford, & Feinstein, 1996). The offense mobility pattern (1.80%) is less likely to occur in residences ($\beta = -2.02$, $p < .05$) and usually occurs without sexual touching ($\beta = 1.30$, $p < .01$).

In Model 5, the reference category is the total mobility pattern (25.98% of cases). According to the Nagelkerke R^2 , this model explains 36.7% of the variance. The total mobility pattern is less likely to happen when victims are aged between 3 and 9 years old ($\beta = -0.82$, $p < .01$) and 10 and 12 years old ($\beta = -0.78$, $p < .01$). Child abuse is less frequent when the crime takes place in a residence ($\beta = -1.37$, $p < .001$). This pattern occurs more often when abuse takes place in public places ($\beta = 1.65$, $p < .01$), entertainment locations ($\beta = 1.46$,

$p < .001$) or outside ($\beta = 0.82, p < .01$). Offenders are less frequently familiar with the place of aggression ($\beta = -0.73, p < .01$).

[PLEASE INSERT TABLE 5 HERE]

Discussion

Journey to Crime and Victimization

This study analyzed the distances between offenders and victims' residences, and place of crimes. In general, the results corroborate the distance decay hypothesis identified by the literature (Alston, 1994; Andresen and colleagues, 2014; Block and colleagues, 2007; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; Davies & Dale, 1995; LeBeau, 1987a, 1987b, 1987c, 1992). However, compared to sexual assaults against adults, spatial patterns are more concentrated around the first 10 km in all the distances considered. We observed a major difference from the distance between offenders' and victims' living spaces: more than 50% of child assaults are committed within a distance of 1 km (median of 0.77 km), while for adults, the median is 2.65 km. A similar pattern can be detected for the distance between an offender's residence and the place of crime. For child abuse, we found a median of 2.32 km whereas this distance is 4.35 km for adult assaults. It may be counterintuitive to remark that differences between victims' residences and places of crime are less relevant (median 0.24 km for child abuse and 0.62 km for adult assaults). These findings suggest that the limited victim spatial patterns affect the spatial behavior of offenders. Compared to adult sexual assaults, offenders are living closer to their victims and, when selecting the place of crime, they are more subject to the victims' routine activities (Leclerc & Felson, 2016; Smallbone & Wortley, 2000). In child sexual aggression, the habits of the target play a pivotal role in shaping offender spatial patterns, since victims of child abuse are more likely to be supervised and have fixed routines.

The specificity of sexual aggression against children may explain why the data did not detect any buffer zone around an offender's residence. According to Brantingham and

Brantingham (2008), offenders avoid searching for targets around their living spaces. The underlying hypothesis, according to the rational choice theory (Cornish & Clarke, 1986) (Cornish & Clarke, 1986), is that offenders establish “no crime commission” areas around their residences in order to minimize the risk of being identified by neighbors with whom they may interact on a daily basis. However, in sexual crimes against children, opportunities arise from a combination of regular interaction; manipulative strategies; interpersonal trust between the offender, victim, and victim’s guardians (Leclerc, Proulx, Lussier, and colleagues, 2009; Rebocho & Gonçalves, 2012); and accessibility to the target living space. From this perspective, we can hypothesize that geographic proximity naturally facilitates interactions, thus generating more confidence and more opportunities to access to the victim. As a result, an offender may perceive taking advantage of his proximity to the victim (without considering the buffer zone) as a more rational choice, while the need to reduce the risk of being apprehended may be managed using the trust relationship to manipulate the victim’s reaction.

Crime Mobility Triangles

Although child mobility is more limited than that of adults, studying spatial patterns reveals different typologies in child abuse. In particular, in our sample there are four main clusters of the geographic pattern of crime typology. Three of them are more or less equivalent in terms of size: offender mobility, neighborhood mobility, and total mobility. Each one represents around one quarter of the cases. To a lesser extent, we can also observe that few cases are in a victim mobility pattern while thus included in the offense mobility scheme are anecdotal. Compared to previous studies based on adult victims, results confirm that the limited mobility of child victims affects spatial crime typologies (Amir, 1971; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018). For children, all the mobility pattern distances are shorter. For adults, the total mobility triangle is largely prevalent followed by offender mobility while neighborhood mobility covers only a small part (11.65%) of the cases.

Individual Characteristics, Modus Operandi Characteristics and Crime Mobility

Usually, factors influencing mobility patterns depend on individual characteristics and modus operandi. For child sexual assault, the age of the victim plays a major role in explaining the variation in mobility patterns. These findings stand in stark contrast with a previous study on adult sexual victims where individual characteristics were not relevant (Chopin & Caneppele, 2018).

The youngest children (3 to 9 years old) are less mobile and tend to spend most of their routine days at home or at supervised locations (Leclerc & Felson, 2016; Smallbone & Wortley, 2000), and these are the places where they are victimized. Preadolescents and adolescents (10 to 12 years old and 13 to 14 years old) start to be more independent by changing their routine activities and consequently by increasing their mobility. This change corresponds to their secondary socialization (e.g., meeting peers or making friends), which affects the risk of victim exposure to sexual aggression since the probability of meeting a motivated offender during routine activities (or while traveling to them) increases. Another element that explains the augmented risk, may be linked to a lack of worldly experience during preadolescence and adolescence. Young victims may not clearly distinguish between what is acceptable and what is not in terms of sexual behavior, so they can be easily manipulated (Leclerc, Proulx, Lussier, and colleagues, 2009; Rebocho & Gonçalves, 2012), especially when offenders are relatives, close to the family, or occupy institutional positions (e.g., as teachers, trainers, priests, or caregivers). Moreover, the age of an offender does not seem linked to any particular spatial pattern, and this is in line with the literature on adult sexual offenders (Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; LeBeau, 1987a). Unlike previous studies that observed a relationship between modus operandi and offender characteristics (Leclerc and colleagues, 2006; Leclerc, Proulx, Lussier, and colleagues, 2009), the offender characteristics considered in our research do not provide any explanation for spatial behavior in child sexual abuse in our models.

Our findings corroborate the hypothesis that stranger sexual offenders against children have to be more mobile than acquaintances (Proulx, Ouimet, & Lachaine, 1995). This could correspond both to opportunistic and/or predatory schemes, which could also explain why in the triangle mobility pattern the presence of weapons and the blitz approach occur more frequently than in the other patterns where cons are more often used (Leclerc and colleagues, 2016). The location of aggression is also relevant in order to determine the outcome of the sexual acts performed. When the place is a residence (of the victim or the offender), sexual acts are more severe. Like adult victims, this could be explained by the fact that offenders consider residences safe environments (Chopin & Caneppele, 2018; Keating, Higgs, Willott, & Stedman, 1990; Quinsey & Upfold, 1985).

The use of the geographic mobility pattern provides further peculiarities for each spatial scheme. Under the neighborhood mobility pattern, the assault is more often perpetrated against children and, to a lesser extent, against adolescents while they are in the areas close to their residences. Offenders are acquaintances, they exploit trust relationships, and they live in the same neighborhoods. They sometimes hide paraphilic disorders (Leclerc, Proulx, & Beauregard, 2009), but they tend to be part of their communities and lead balanced lives (are not loners or people with no active social lives). The offender mobility pattern recalls a more predatory scheme. Offenders and victims rarely know each other, and the assault tends to be perpetrated in a closed environment such as a residence, the offender's workplace, or a transportation-related location while the victim is engaged in domestic activities (e.g., watching TV, reading a book, or eating).

In the victim mobility pattern, the augmented mobility of preadolescents moves them outside their residences toward an acquaintance's location. Therefore, the probability of being assaulted during a visit to see friends/relatives is higher. We can hypothesize that the augmented risk may depend on the victims' proximity to sexual offenders who may be family

members of the victim's friends and who are often young adults (brothers, uncles, or fathers) with active social lives. This hypothesis is supported by the existence of a higher probability of being assaulted during babysitting. Following the same mechanism, sexual offenders may be the babysitter or found among the babysitter's friends, who are usually also young adults. The total mobility pattern, coherent with our previous hypothesis on victim mobility, is associated with adolescence (13 to 14 years old). Due to their age, this group is more mobile and less supervised. This is why offenders are more opportunistic and are not necessarily familiar with the place of crime. They assault victims more often in non-domestic public and private contexts such as public places, open spaces, entertainment locations, and areas associated with their friends. The offense mobility pattern is the only model that does not readily fit with child sexual abusers. The number of cases that fall into this category is in fact limited, and the statistical analysis does not provide a robust interpretation.

[PLEASE INSERT TABLE 6 HERE]

Conclusion

Main Results and Implications

This research discussed the spatial mobility of child sexual abuse through the lenses of the journey to crime and to victimization and associated factors. This explorative research had three general aims. The first one assumed the existence of a distance decay function for extrafamilial sexual abuse against children. Our results support this view, which is consistent with existing knowledge. Nevertheless, in our sample we observed the lack of a buffer zone that does not seem to be consistent with the field of extrafamilial sexual assaults based on what previous studies have shown (e.g. Block and colleagues, 2007; Chopin & Caneppele, 2018). This can be explained by the fact that when routine activity patterns are limited and supervised, interactions between victims and offenders occur mainly in the victim's residence or in the immediate surroundings. By contrast, we may also assume that the solved cases considered in

our analysis include a specific subsample of offenders that are getting caught specifically because they did not respect the buffer zone. The existence of a buffer zone comprised in the 0 to 250 m distance to the offender's living space could also be considered as an alternative explanation although in the sample 17.97% of child sexual abuses take place in the same location (apartment or building) where both offender and victim live.

The second aim assumed the feasibility of clustering child sexual abuse cases in crime mobility triangle typologies. Our analysis confirms that cases of child abuse can be classified in geometric and geographic patterns of crime typologies. From a scientific perspective, the use of typologies should improve the understanding of the phenomenon. The heuristic aspect of a classification should also be considered for mobility crime triangles. The offense mobility pattern does not seem to provide a robust heuristic value, but as a rare event it must be considered in further research and needs to be analyzed in detail.

The last general aim focuses on the role of modus operandi when explaining variance in spatial patterns. The study partially refutes this view. Modus operandi remains important to explain spatial patterns, especially for the aspects linked to the relationship between offender, victim and environment of aggression. Moreover, we identified the pivotal role of the victim's age. This variable should be interpreted as a proxy indicator of routine activities in terms of mobility variance and supervision. Children move less and are more closely supervised than preadolescents, and preadolescents move less and are more closely supervised than adolescents.

This research on the mobility of child abuse provide further support to the environmental paradigm. In particular, it emerges that journeys to crime are affected by children routine activities. Our results may yield practical implications for criminal investigations and crime prevention. First, law enforcement may use the distance decay and the triangle mobility construct to formulate investigative hypotheses. Second, findings may

suggest the significance of educating families and institutions of providing guidance to preadolescents and adolescents regarding which social behaviors are acceptable and which are not because they violate a child's physical and sexual integrity as indicated by Wortley and Smallbone (2006).

Data Limitation

This study presents some data limitations and bias in the interpretation of the findings. First, it should be noted that the triangle mobility pattern often turns into a polygon mobility pattern. It is not possible to exclude that offenders and victims have multiple residences while mobility crime triangle considers that both of them have only one address.

Second, the analysis focused on cases reported and solve by the police. Our findings cannot be applied to unreported and/or unsolved cases that could have different characteristics. In that perspective, we could argue that the representativeness of this study is limited. There is a lack of official data available on the number of unreported cases of child abuse in France, but Chopin (2017), for sexual extrafamilial rapes, indicated a reporting rate of 16%. As this study uses reported child abuses, the findings should be tempered and could be applied only to a minority of cases.

Third, geographic patterns of crime were based on a theoretical construction, following the previous studies based on the classical 400 m distance. This choice was made to have a better comparability between our findings and those concerning adult victims. Nevertheless, it is possible that another distance is more appropriate to characterize the neighborhood for children due to their situational mobility constraints.

Fourth, the sample is based on cases occurred from 1979 to 2013. During this period, important changes in terms of human mobility and transportation occurred. This aspect must be considered and can induce bias in the interpretation of the data.

Fifth, our theoretical framework relies on routine activities theory and rational choice approach, which have been used by other studies on child sexual abuse. Due to a lack of information in our database, we have not considered the mental health characteristics.

Some methodological choices made in this research can have an impact in terms of interpretation of the findings. First of all, the variable related to the age of the victim had been transformed in categorical variables mirroring the four childhood stages. If this choice facilitated the comprehension of the findings, it could also affect their interpretation (see MacCallum, Zhang, Preacher, & Rucker, 2002). Second, the use of a large number of bivariate analysis to select multivariate specifications can result in bias (see e.g., Sun, Shook, & Kay, 1996). Specifically, it can lead to a potential inflation of Type 1 error. Third, in comparing mobility patterns, we adopted a series of binomial regressions instead of multinomial regression to compare at a multivariate level the different categories. This choice has been made because the number of cases in the offense mobility patterns were rare. Methodological problems of rare events with logistic regression have been highlighted (see King & Zeng, 2001; Peduzzi and colleagues, 1996) and can led to several bias as for example an overrepresentation of odds ratio. Therefore, multivariate findings must be interpreted with caution by considering trends more than more than odds ratio. Moreover, by using a series of binomial regressions instead of multinomial regression, multivariate models are less precise. Fourth, the study does not make a distinction between extrafamilial child sexual abusers who have a trust relationship with the victim and the victim's family, and those who are strangers to them. The findings suggest that the existence/absence of a relationship of trust may reveal important differences in mobility patterns. Fourth, the study does not contemplate the distinction between urban and rural areas. Although the results seem to indicate that urbanization has not been important since young victims have limited mobility, this hypothesis should be tested in the future.

Research perspective

Further research is also needed to investigate the complexities of crime mobility, going beyond the simplified model of the crime triangle, in order to promote a more detailed classification of sexual offenders not only by their targets or motives but also by their mobility patterns. In addition, other studies should focus on very specific subtypologies of extrafamilial sexual offenders, analyzing the relationship between mobility patterns, modus operandi, offender and victim characteristics, and the existence of a social relationship. In this perspective, variables on mental illness should be considered to analyze their influence on the mobility of child abusers. Further studies analyzing spatial behavior of child abuses should also test empirically the best distance to characterize the neighborhood concept and determinate if the 400 m distance is a constant or if neighborhood concept varies depending on the age of victims. As shown in the introduction, there is a lack of knowledge on the spatial pattern of child sexual abuse. The issue of data accessibility may represent the main reason why researchers have barely discussed this topic. To collect spatial data, researchers have two methodological options. They can rely on police data, or they can conduct primary data collection through interviews with offenders and victims. Both options have strengths and pitfalls. Police data allow researchers to aggregate individual spatial patterns and assure the possibility of detecting a crime template (Brantingham & Brantingham, 1981). However, such data are only a subsample of a larger phenomenon (due to the low reporting rate) and they cannot provide information about individual motives and the reason for mobility. In terms of accessibility, researchers must obtain authorization to deal with sensitive data, which is not always granted due to confidentiality reasons. Data quality may also be hampered by incomplete addresses or missing information. Meanwhile, interviews with offenders and victims provide detailed descriptions of the journey to crime. They could reveal a more complex spatial pattern (e.g., intermediate stops) and, combined with temporal information, a more complete picture of the specific case of child sexual abuse. However, researchers should

be careful to consider the honesty of any responses given, and they should also consider the possibility of incorrect or incomplete reconstruction of the event due to the time lag. Moreover, the generalization of results cannot be achieved. In terms of accessibility, interviews are more difficult to conduct since they require both finding and getting the consent of offenders, victims, and any institutions involved (e.g., a penitentiary, psychiatric hospital, or victim support association). In terms of feasibility, data collection through interviews requires more temporal and economic resources.

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Appendix

Appendix A.

Distance distribution from 0 to 10 km (N=612)

Km	O-Prime		V-Prime		O-V	
	<i>n</i>	% Cum	<i>n</i>	% Cum	<i>n</i>	% Cum
0 - 0.25	154	25.16%	305	49.84%	256	41.83%
0.25 - 0.5	38	31.37%	51	58.17%	24	45.75%
0.5 - 0.75	26	35.62%	34	63.73%	21	49.18%
0.75 - 1	1	35.78%	20	66.99%	19	52.29%
1 - 1.25	24	39.71%	18	69.93%	16	54.90%
1.25 - 1.5	20	42.97%	12	71.90%	10	56.54%
1.5 - 1.75	22	46.57%	15	74.35%	10	58.17%
1.75 - 2	9	48.04%	6	75.33%	4	58.82%
2 - 2.25	7	49.18%	9	76.80%	8	60.13%
2.25 - 2.5	9	50.65%	4	77.45%	6	61.11%
2.5 - 2.75	7	51.80%	5	78.27%	6	62.09%
2.75 - 3	7	52.94%	2	78.59%	10	63.73%
3 - 3.25	11	54.74%	4	79.25%	13	65.85%
3.25 - 3.5	11	56.54%	3	79.74%	8	67.16%
3.5 - 3.75	6	57.52%	4	80.39%	7	68.30%
3.75 - 4	4	58.17%	6	81.37%	4	68.95%
4 - 4.25	5	58.99%	4	82.03%	2	69.28%
4.25 - 4.5	3	59.48%	0	82.03%	6	70.26%
4.5 - 4.75	9	60.95%	2	82.35%	2	70.59%
4.75 - 5	8	62.25%	1	82.52%	6	71.57%
5 - 5.25	3	62.75%	3	83.01%	3	72.06%
5.25 - 5.5	1	62.91%	1	83.17%	1	72.22%
5.5 - 5.75	3	63.40%	1	83.33%	3	72.71%
5.75 - 6	5	64.22%	4	83.99%	1	72.88%
6 - 6.25	2	64.54%	1	84.15%	2	73.20%
6.25 - 6.5	3	65.03%	1	84.31%	3	73.69%
6.5 - 6.75	4	65.69%	1	84.48%	1	73.86%
6.75 - 7	2	66.01%	1	84.64%	2	74.18%
7 - 7.25	3	66.50%	3	85.13%	2	74.51%
7.25 - 7.5	7	67.65%	1	85.29%	2	74.84%
7.5 - 7.75	4	68.30%	2	85.62%	4	75.49%

7.75 - 8	4	68.95%	1	85.78%	2	75.82%
8 - 8.25	3	69.44%	1	85.95%	1	75.98%
8.25 - 8.5	6	70.42%	2	86.27%	3	76.47%
8.5 - 8.75	2	70.75%	1	86.44%	3	76.96%
8.75 - 9	2	71.08%	3	86.93%	3	77.45%
9 - 9.25	2	71.41%	2	87.25%	3	77.94%
9.25 - 9.5	2	71.73%	3	87.75%	3	78.43%
9.5 - 9.75	6	72.71%	2	88.07%	2	78.76%
9.75 - 10	1	72.88%	1	88.24%	1	78.92%
Total	446		540		483	

Tables and Figures

Table 1.

Distribution of the intervals of distances for the cases of sexual crimes (N=612)

Distance interval	Offender-Place of crime		Victim-Place of crime		Offender-Victim	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
0 – 10 Km	446	72.88%	540	88.24%	482	78.76%
10 – 20 Km	55	8.99%	17	2.78%	38	6.21%
20 – 30 Km	18	2.94%	8	1.31%	15	2.45%
30 – 40 Km	15	2.45%	3	0.49%	12	1.96%
40 – 50 Km	13	2.12%	4	0.65%	9	1.47%
> 50 Km	65	10.62%	40	6.54%	56	9.15%
Total	612	100.00	612	100.00	612	100.00
Mean (Km)	28.26		19.48		22.80	
Median (Km)	2.32		0.24		0.77	

Figure 1. Distance decay function displaying the first 0 – 5 km (N=612)

Table 2:

Corresponding table between the geometric triangle typology and the geographic triangle typology (N=612)

	Dots		Lines		Triangles		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Neighborhood	110	100.00%	48	18.11%	9	3.80%	167	27.29%
Offender mobility	0	0.00%	127	47.92%	43	18.14%	170	27.78%
Victim mobility	0	0.00%	85	32.08%	20	8.44%	105	17.16%
Offence mobility	0	0.00%	5	1.89%	6	2.53%	11	1.80%
Total mobility	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	159	67.09%	159	25.98%
Total	110	17.97%	265	43.30%	237	38.73%	612	100.00%

Table 3.

Distribution of the victims and offenders' characteristics according to the geometric patterns of crime (N=612)

	Total		Dots		Lines		Triangles		Cramer's V & Phi/F		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	a	b	c
Victim Characteristics			110	17.97%	265	43.30%	237	38.73%			
Victim is a female	420	68.63%	70	63.64%	178	67.17%	172	72.57%	0.034	0.091†	0.059
Victim between 0 and 2 y/o	6	0.98%	0	0.00%	6	2.26%	0	0.00%	¹ 2,530	/	¹ 5.431*
Victim between 3 and 9 y/o	278	45.42%	69	62.73%	127	47.92%	82	34.60%	0.135†	0.109*	0.135**
Victim between 10 and 12 y/o	199	32.52%	27	24.55%	88	33.21%	84	35.44%	0.086	0.109*	0.024
Victim between 13 and 14 y/o	129	21.08%	14	12.73%	44	16.60%	71	29.96%	0.049	0.245***	0.159***
Routine activities											
Domestic activities	79	12.91%	23	20.91%	44	16.60%	12	5.06%	0.051	0.245***	0.183***
Sleeping	56	9.15%	16	14.55%	35	13.21%	5	2.11%	0.018	0.243***	0.205***
School activities	19	3.10%	4	3.64%	6	2.26%	9	3.80%	0.039	0.004	0.045
Babysitting	46	7.52%	8	7.27%	35	13.21%	3	1.27%	0.085	¹ 8,832**	0.160
Playing	211	34.48%	48	43.64%	92	34.72%	71	29.96%	0.084	0.134*	0.051
Travelling from to or from somewhere	165	26.96%	17	15.45%	48	18.11%	100	42.19%	0.032	0.263***	0.264***
Sports or recreational activities	101	16.50%	15	13.64%	36	13.58%	50	21.10%	0.001	0.089†	0.100*
Visiting friends/relatives	98	16.01%	24	21.82%	54	20.38%	20	8.44%	0.016	0.187***	0.168***

Offender			110	17.97%	265	43.30%	237	38.73%			
Characteristics											
Offender is a male	610	99.67%	109	99.09%	264	99.62%	237	100.00%	¹ 0,414	¹ 2,161	¹ 0,896
Age			32.45 ^{2,3} [16.85] ⁴		34,25 ² [14.83] ⁴		35,00 ² [14.91] ⁴				
Offender is single	332	54.25%	64	58.18%	146	55.09%	122	51.48%	0.028	0.063	0.036
Offender living with nobody	147	24.02%	18	16.36%	70	26.42%	59	24.89%	0.108*	0.096†	0.017
Lifestyle											
Offender consumes alcohol	100	16.34%	19	17.27%	43	16.23%	38	16.03%	0.013	0.016	0.003
Offender consumes drug	16	2.61%	3	2.73%	1	0.38%	12	5.06%	¹ 0,438	¹ 0,991	0.053
Offender like to socialize/party	53	8.66%	4	3.64%	38	14.34%	11	4.64%	0.155**	0.023	0.163***
Offender is loner	112	18.30%	19	17.27%	55	20.75%	38	16.03%	0.040	0.016	0.061
Offender is frequently engage in criminal activities	43	7.03%	4	3.64%	21	7.92%	18	7.59%	0.078	0.076	0.006
Evidence of paraphilic behavior	239	39.05%	56	50.91%	100	37.74%	83	35.02%	0.122*	0.151*	0.028

¹: Fisher's exact test

²: Represent the mean

³: Kruskal-Wallis Test have been used. No significant differences were found

⁴: Standard deviation

Diff sig: *** p≤0.001, ** p≤0.01, * p≤0.05, † p≤0.1

a: Comparison between dot and line patterns

b: Comparison between dot and triangle patterns

c: Comparison between line and triangle patterns

Table 4.

Distribution of the modus operandi characteristics according to the geometric patterns of crime (N= 612)

	Total		Dots		Lines		Triangles		Cramer's V & Phi/F		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	a	b	c
Aggression			110	17.97%	265	43.30%	237	38.73%			
Relationship offender-victim											
Victim and offender are stranger	259	42.32%	13	11.82%	81	30.57%	165	69.62%	0.197***	0.538***	0.390***
Victim and offender are acquaintance	353	57.68%	97	88.18%	184	69.43%	72	30.38%	0.235***	0.581***	0.412***
Type of approach¹											
Con approach	511	83.50%	97	88.18%	226	85.28%	188	79.32%	0.038	0.108*	0.078†
Surprise approach	78	12.75%	11	10.00%	31	11.70%	36	15.19%	0.025	0.071	0.051
Blitz approach	36	5.88%	3	2.73%	10	3.77%	23	9.70%	² 0,254	0.123*	0.119†
Place of aggression											
Residence	386	63.07%	98	89.09%	224	84.53%	64	27.00%	0.060	0.579***	0.581***
Offender workplace	50	8.17%	2	1.82%	25	9.43%	23	9.70%	0.134†	0.142**	0.005
Transportation related location	40	6.54%	1	0.91%	18	6.79%	21	8.86%	0.122*	0.152**	0.039
Entertainment location	14	2.29%	0	0.00%	5	1.89%	9	3.80%	² 2,104	² 4,288*	0.111
Public building	55	8.99%	2	1.82%	10	3.77%	43	18.14%	² 0,960	0.226***	0.233***
Outside place	234	38.24%	20	18.18%	62	23.40%	152	64.14%	0.057	0.428***	0.411***
Offender is familiar with the place	548	89.54%	108	98.18%	249	93.96%	191	80.59%	0.090†	0.237***	0.203***
Type of sexual aggression²											
Sexual penetration	251	41.01%	58	52.73%	110	41.51%	83	35.02%	0.103*	0.168**	0.067
Sexual touching	474	77.45%	95	86.36%	201	75.85%	178	75.11%	0.117*	0.128*	0.009
Foreplay	348	56.86%	65	59.09%	167	63.02%	116	48.95%	0.037	0.095†	0.142**
Presence of weapon	43	7.03%	1	0.91%	15	5.66%	27	11.39%	² 4,296*	0.179***	0.103*

Diff sig: *** p≤0.001, ** p≤0.01, * p≤0.05, † p≤0.1

a: Comparison between dot and line patterns

b: Comparison between dot and triangle patterns

c: Comparison between line and triangle patterns

¹:Total can be more than 100% if two approaches are combined (e.g., con + surprise)

²:Fisher's exact test

³:Total can be more than 100% if different types of sexual acts are committed during the aggression

Table 5.
 Logistic regressions of factors influencing each triangle mobility patterns (N=612)

	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4		Model 5	
	^a Neighborhood		^a Offender mobility		^a Victim mobility		^a Offence mobility		^a Total mobility	
	mobility pattern		pattern		pattern		pattern		pattern	
	Vs other cases		Vs other cases		Vs other cases		Vs other cases		Vs other cases	
	β	Exp(β)	β	Exp(β)	β	Exp(β)	β	Exp(β)	β	Exp(β)
Victim between 3 and 9 y/o	1.138	3.121***	0.729	2.073**	-0.712	0.491**			-0.822	0.439**
Victim between 10 and 12 y/o	0.586	1.798†	0.763	2.144**					-0.778	0.459**
Domestic activities			0.715	2.044*	-1.094	0.335*				
Babysitting					0.710	2.034*			-1.134	0.322†
Victim was travelling	0.928	2.530**			-1.016	0.362**				
Victim was visiting friends			-1.239	0.290***	0.961	2.615***				
Offender living with nobody	-0.632	0.532*							0.522	1.686*
Offender like to socialize/party	-1.510	0.221**			0.641	1.898†				
Evidence of paraphilic behavior	0.388	1.475*								
Victim and offender are acquaintances	1.717	5.565***	-1.434	0.238***	0.731	2.076*				
Con approach	-0.591	0.554†								
Residence	0.924	2.520**	1.300	3.668***			-2.017	0.133*	-1.371	0.254***
Offender workplace	-1.691	0.184**	0.759	2.136*						
Transportation related location	-1.535	0.215*	1.110	3.036**						
Public place			-0.937	0.392*					1.648	4.321**
Entertainment location									1.464	5.195***
Outdoor place									0.821	2.272**
Offender is familiar with the place	1.606	4.980*							-0.729	0.482**
Sexual touching	0.679	1.972*					-1.590	0.204*		
Foreplay					0.429	1.536†				
Any use of weapon	-2.592	0.075*								
Constant	-5.087	0.006***	-1.634	0.195***	-2.099	0.123***	0.795	2.214	0.189	1.209†
n of the reference category	167		170		105		11		159	
% of the reference category	27.29%		27.78%		17.16%		1.80%		25.98%	
χ^2	182.346***		101.156***		82.310***		49.651***		176.565***	
2*log likelihood	535.346		622.035		478.729		60.564		524.605	
Cox and Snell R ²	0.258		0.152		0.126		0.078		0.251	
Nagelkerke R ²	0.373		0.220		0.210		0.410		0.367	

Overclassification	79.10%	77.80%	82.80%	98.70%	78.60%
Sensitivity ¹	0.64	0.69	0.61	0.80	0.60
Specificity ²	0.83	0.79	0.85	0.99	0.84

Diff sig: *** p≤0.001, ** p≤0.01, * p≤0.05, † p≤0.1

^a:Reference category

$$1. \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}}$$

$$2. \frac{\text{True Negative}}{\text{False Positive} + \text{True Negative}}$$

Table 6.

Risk factors positively and negatively associated to the mobility triangle pattern typologies¹

	Risk factors positively associated	Risk factors negatively associated
Neighborhood	Victim aged between 3 to 9 y/o	Offender lives alone
mobility	Victim was travelling	Offender like socialize
	Offender have paraphilic disorders	Assault occurs in offender workplace
	Victim and offenders are acquaintances	Assault occurs in transportation related location
	Assault occurs in a residence	Offender use weapon
	Offender is familiar with the place of crime	
	Offender performs sexual touching	
Offender	Victim aged between 3 to 12 y/o	Victim was visiting
mobility	Victim is assaulted during domestic activities	Victim and offender are acquaintance
	Assault occurs in a residence	Assault occurs in a public place
	Assault occurs in offender workplace	
	Assault occurs in a transportation related location	
Victim mobility	Victim is assaulted during babysitting	Victim aged of 3 to 9 y/o
	Victim is assaulted during a visit to friends or relatives	Victim is assaulted during domestic activities
	Victim and offenders are acquaintances	Victim was travelling
	Offender performs foreplays	
Offence mobility		Assault occurs in a residence
		Offender performs sexual touching
Total mobility	Victim is assaulted during a visit to friends or relatives	Victim aged between 3 to 12 y/o
	Assault occurs in a public place	Assault occurs in a residence
	Assault occurs outdoor	Offender is familiar with the place of crime

Assault occurs entertainment location

¹ Only findings with a pvalue minor or equal to 0.05 are reported in the table